

Gregory of Nyssa "On the Soul and the Resurrection"

also known as "De Anima et Resurrectione"

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** Expert Source entry, prepared by a Ph.D. RA or DRH Editor from an expert's published work(s), and then personally edited and approved by the expert.*

Entry tags: Christianity, Early Christianity, Religious Group, Byzantine, Greek, Theology text, Text, Christian Theology, Early Christian Text, Language, Byzantine text, Orthodoxy

Gregory of Nyssa, the younger brother of St. Basil the Great (c. 330-379) was born around 330 and was educated chiefly by Basil, at the family's monastic convent near the river Iris, in Cappadocia. Like his older brother, he opted at first for a secular career in rhetoric. Unlike Basil however, he even got married. Under the influence of his close friends, especially Gregory of Nazianzus (c. 329-389), he retired to the same monastery on the Iris which his brother, Basil, founded. In 371, his ecclesiastical career advanced further, being elevated to the episcopal seat of Nyssa (in modern central Turkey), a small town in St. Basil's metropolitan district of Caesarea. Not being able to cope with administrative tasks as efficiently as his brother, Basil, Gregory lacked the diplomatic skills that would help him to deal with the ecclesiastical issues -mainly the Arian teachings and their influence- of his time. Despite his political levity, Gregory was a charismatic writer and a theologian, well versed in both the Scriptures and secular philosophy. His work "On the Soul and the Resurrection" is one of the most influential works of Orthodox Patristic literature. After St. Basil's death in early 379, Gregory visited his sister, Macrina, at the convent on the river Iris where she was the abbess. Here he sought consolation concerning the recent loss of his brother, only to find that his sister too was soon to die. Modeled upon the deathbed dialogue of Socrates in Plato's, "Phaedo", Gregory composes a deathbed dialogue between his sister and himself wherein he plays the "devil's advocate" while Macrina presents the proper Christian understanding concerning the immortality of the soul and the hope of the resurrection. The ideas attributed to Macrina are those of the author himself. In this deathbed discussion, Macrina and Gregory reason out the philosophical underpinnings of the Christian's hope: human reason enlightened by the Holy Spirit can supplement one's theological endeavors and thus bolster one's faith. Reason, therefore, serves as a handmaiden to theology which can support one's faith when it wavers. Such a method reveals the work's primary audience, namely a Christian one. As a result, the "On the Soul and the Resurrection" displays quite well Gregory's profound philosophical and literary learning. It also serves as an example of the positive role secular learning can play in Christian life and thought. The "On the Soul and the Resurrection" therefore displays much of the flexibility toward contemporary Greek though and literary style discussed above. Due to the nature of this work, theological anthropology plays a key role, especially concerning the nature of the human soul in its relationship to the human body and to the divine nature. The theological anthropology which underlies this book will prove very influential in later Orthodox Christian ascetical and theological writings.

Date Range: 335 CE - 394 CE

Region: Nyssa in Cappadocia

Region tags: Anatolia, Asia Minor, Byzantium, Turkey, Cappadocia

Nyssa in Cappadocia, the see of St. Gregory

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: *On the Soul and the Resurrection: St Gregory of Nyssa* (St. Vladimir Seminar Press)
- Source 2: *Gregori Nysseni Opera, Opera dogmatica minora, pars III - De Anima Et Resurrectione*, 2014, Brill (Andreas Spira)
- Source 3: Mateo-Seco, Lucas Francisco; Maspero, Giulio, eds. (2010). *The Brill Dictionary of Gregory of Nyssa*. Leiden: Brill.
- Source 1: *Grégoire de Nysse Sur l'âme et la résurrection*, trans. Jean Terrieux, 1995
- Source 2: *Grégoire De Nysse, L'ÂME ET LA RÉSURRECTION : DIALOGUE AVEC SA SOEUR MACRINE*, 2011
- Source 3: Morwenna Ludlow (2007). *Gregory of Nyssa : ancient and (post)modern*. Oxford University Press. ISBN 978-0-19-928076-6.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://afkimel.wordpress.com/2020/02/16/apprehending-apokatastasis-the-vision-of-st-gregory-of-nyssa/>
- Source 1 Description: *Apprehending Apokatastasis: The Vision of St Gregory of Nyssa*
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.newadvent.org/cathen/07016a.htm>
- Source 1 Description: *St. Gregory of Nyssa* (Catholic Encyclopedia)
- Source 2 URL: https://apostoliki-diakonia.gr/en_main/catehism/theologia_zoi/themata.asp?contents=selides_katixisis/contents_Texts.asp&main=SK_texts&file=13.htm
- Source 2 Description: *Gregory of Nyssa on the Nature of the Soul*
- Source 3 URL: <https://philosophicaleggs.com/107-st-gregory-on-the-souls-principles-of-organization/>
- Source 3 Description: *St. Gregory of Nyssa on the origins and nature of the soul*
- Source 1 URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20080513192134/http://www.sage.edu/faculty/salomd/nyssa/index.html>
- Source 1 Description: *The Gregory of Nyssa Home Page*
- Source 2 URL: <https://classicalstudies.org/irrational-parts-soul-%E2%80%9Cagainst-nature%E2%80%9D-christian-neoplatonism-gregory-nyssen-antecedents-origen-and>
- Source 2 Description: *The Irrational Parts of the Soul “Against Nature” in Christian Neoplatonism? Gregory Nyssen with Antecedents in Origen and Aftermath in Evagrius*
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3AJI5fL6cIU>
- Source 3 Description: *On The Soul And The Resurrection, Saint Gregory Of Nyssa, Full-Length Catholic Audiobook*

- Source 1 URL: <https://thehiddenpearl.org/2013/02/18/the-fire-of-purgation-in-gregory-of-nyssas-de-anima-et-resurrectione/>
- Source 1 Description: The fire of purgation in Gregory of Nyssa's "De Anima et Resurrectione"
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.gregor-von-nyssa.de/>
- Source 2 Description: Gregory of Nyssa
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.uni-muenster.de/EvTheol/en/gvn/index.html>
- Source 3 Description: Forschungsstelle Gregor von Nyssa

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.newadvent.org/fathers/2915.htm>
- Source 1 Description: St. Gregory of Nyssa, On the soul and the resurrection
- Source 2 URL: https://www.documentacatholicaomnia.eu/20_30_0330-0395-_Gregorius_Nyssenus,_Sanctus.html
- Source 2 Description: Gregorius Nyssenus, Sanctus (Documenta Catholica Omnia)

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

Inked

- with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Papyrus

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: In line with Plato's literary example, Gregory wrote a dramatic dialogue regarding the soul and the resurrection of the bodies, in which he plays the role of the ignorant pupil, who doubts about Christianity's teachings, while his elder sister Macrina assumes the role of teacher, who wishes to prove to the pupil the validity of Christian doctrines. The lively dialogue addresses many thorny issues, with a particular importance for the intellectual milieu of the 4th century, such as the nature of the soul, the condition of the soul after death, and the transmigration of the soul. Gregory's adherence to Scripture in the context of his philosophical milieu provides contemporary readers with a superb example of Christianity encountering culture.

Reference: Meredith, Anthony . The Cappadocians. Crestwood, NY: St. Vladimir's Seminary Press, 1995.

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?

(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: Gregory begins his discussion on the soul by raising two objections: a) assuming that the soul is complex and composed of the same elements as the body, it is dissolved in death together with the body, and b) if the soul is of a different nature than the body it cannot be in it and if it is not in the body it cannot exist at all since there is no other place where it could be. This assumes that for the soul to exist in the body it must have the same nature as the body. Here the soul would exist only until the dissolution of the body. But if the soul does not share the body's nature, it cannot exist at all since it cannot then be in the body and there is no other place for it in the universe. Macrina discredits these objections as being opinions held by the Stoics and Epicureans. The latter, she accuses of understanding nature to be fortuitous, automatic, and without providential oversight. Appearance therefore defines nature and sensation is the means to knowing it. Such opinions, according to Macrina, the "spokesman" of Christian teaching, are the result of a spiritual blindness which comes from excluding the intellectual realities which are known only by the mind. Another objection follows: the soul, according to Gregory, who plays the role of the "devil's advocate", is not visible, not dimensional, not material, and so forth. But the question is what the soul is. Macrina replies that much is learned from negative assertions, even the very being of the thing being pondered. Goodness is presented as not evil. The nature of cowardice is well revealed in the term unmanliness. One can understand the nature of better qualities through the denial of the worse, and vice versa, the nature of evil by the deprivation of good qualities. Since the soul can be inferred to exist from its activities, such negative concepts define it well. One would learn thereby that the soul is incomprehensible to the senses, without weight, size, dimension, location, or any of the qualities of matter.

Reference: Vasilescu, Elena Ene. "The Epektasis [ἐπέκτασις] and the Exploits of the Soul (ἡ Ψυχὴ) in Gregory of Nyssa's *De Anima Et Resurrectione/on the Soul and the Resurrection*". In *Glimpses into Byzantium Its Philosophy and Arts*, 140–58. Oxford: Blackwell, 2021.

Reference: Corrigan, Kevin. *Evagrius and Gregory Mind, Soul and Body in the 4th Century*. Oxon: Routledge, 2016.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: No other categories are present.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Reference: Daniélou, Jean. "La Résurrection Des Corps. Chez Grégoire De Nysse". *Vigiliae Christianae* 7, no. 3 (1953): 154–70.

Reference: Bovon, François , and Mireille Hébert. "Retour De L'âme : Immortalité Et Résurrection Dans Le Christianisme Primitif". *Études Théologiques Et Religieuses* 86, no. 4 (2011): 433–53. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3917/etr.0864.0433>.

- ↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime
 - No
- ↳ At specified time in future
 - No
- ↳ At unspecified time in near future
 - No
- ↳ At unspecified time in distant future
 - Yes
- ↳ At some other time [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - No
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - No

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– Yes

Notes: The text explores the notion of fire as an agent of purification in the afterlife, based on a biblical foundation, upon which Gregory relied to expound his teachings. Catharsis from evil can be achieved before the human soul is separated from the body or afterward. After their death, the Saints will immediately be joined to the Beautiful, for they lived a virtuous life by taming their anger and desire (passions) rejecting evil. However, not all human beings are Saints. Some, through “error of judgment as to the true Beauty” and “the growth of delusion,” will exercise their free will to choose vice rather than virtue, tainting thus their souls with evil. The soul of such a human being becomes intermingled with evil, which is not of the soul’s essence. Death separates the created and immortal soul from the body with which she was created but does not separate her from her bondage to passions. Therefore, a “second death” is necessary for the soul to be restored to the Good. According to Gregory, fire rids the soul of the evil amassed throughout one’s life. Evil is the product of sin, the misuse of free will and reason, both of which God has given to all rational beings. Free will and the faculty of reason separate human beings from brutes to whom “passions belong by nature.” Unfortunately, whenever someone succumbs to passions, the essence of that person’s soul becomes tainted by that which does not belong to it. By the exercise of free will, that person chooses to be reduced to the state of a brute, a state lesser than the Beautiful had intended. Furthermore, death does not separate the soul from her bondage to passions and to this life.

Reference: Maspero, Giulio , Miguel Brugarolas, and Ilaria Vigorelli. *Studia Patristica*. Vol. CI - Gregory of Nyssa's Mystical Eschatology. Leuven: Peeters Publishers, 2021. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv1q26pj0>.

↳ All religious in-group members will survive

– Yes

↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive

– Field doesn't know

↳ All members of the sample region will survive

– Yes

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton

– Yes

Notes: The concept of apokatastasis is an important one in Gregory's thought, appearing very frequently in his writings in a variety of contexts and different applications. The most predominant usage refers to the general resurrection and the restoration of man in the image and likeness of God. Gregory's application of the term that the doctrine of universal restoration is present throughout his work. Gregory interprets apokatastasis as a purely Christian doctrine that entirely depends on the

work of Christ, which encompasses his incarnation, death, and resurrection. Although there is a strong presence of Platonic elements in Gregory's arguments for universal restoration, particularly concerning the accidental nature of evil, the doctrine of apokatastasis does not necessarily rely on apokatastasis theories from pagan philosophy or their accompanying elements. It seems, however, that Gregory considered apokatastasis as a Christian proposition of Platonism, and heavily used Scripture to justify his views. The concept of universal restoration is entirely Christian, merged with a holistic vision of the final resurrection of all. For Gregory, the resurrection is the first stage of the apokatastasis of humankind with the final stage being the restoration to the original state: the resurrection promises us nothing else than the restoration of the fallen to their ancient state.

Reference: Ludlow, Morwenna . Universal Salvation: Eschatology in the Thought of Gregory of Nyssa and Karl Rahner Get Access Arrow. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2000. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1093/0198270224.001.0001>.

Reference: Ramelli, Ilaria . "Apokatastasis and Epektasis in Cant and Origen". In Gregory of Nyssa: In Canticum Canticorum Analytical and Supporting Studies. Proceedings of the 13th International Colloquium on Gregory of Nyssa (rome, 17-20 September 2014), 312-39. Vigiliae Christianae, Supplements. Leiden: Brill, 2018. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004382046_015.

↳ Other survival condition [specify]

– Specify: -

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

- No
- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Cooperation
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Field doesn't know

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Field doesn't know

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Field doesn't know

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Field doesn't know

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Field doesn't know

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: In the text, Macrina appears as the teacher expounding Christian doctrine with reasoned argument. Gregory in fact credits his sister Macrina as the spiritual and theological intelligence behind her siblings' notable careers in the Church. This means that Macrina was not only a fountain of virtue and blessing for the family, but she was also essential in the formation of her brothers' thought, and therefore of Nicene Orthodoxy. In his "On the Soul and the Resurrection" Gregory depicts Macrina as the ideal teacher of Christian faith, who can rebuke any argument.

Reference: Wilson- Kastner, Patricia. "Macrina: Virgin and Teacher". *Andrews University Seminary Studies* 17, no. 1 (1979): 105-17. <https://digitalcommons.andrews.edu/auss/vol17/iss1/10>.

Reference: Silvas, Anna. *Macrina the Younger. Philosopher of God. Medieval Women: Texts and Contexts*. Turnhout: Brepols, 2008.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Gregory of Nyssa "On the Soul and the Resurrection", Peroli, Enrico. "Gregory of Nyssa and the Neoplatonic Doctrine of the Soul". *Vigiliae Christianae* 51, no. 2 (1997): 117-39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/157007297X00011>.

Reference: Gregory of Nyssa "On the Soul and the Resurrection", Zachhuber, Johannes . "The Soul as Dynamis in Gregory of Nyssa's on the Soul and Resurrection". In *Exploring Gregory of Nyssa: Philosophical, Theological, and Historical Studies*, 142-59. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198826422.003.0008>.

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Reference: Gregory of Nyssa "On the Soul and the Resurrection", Canevet, Mariette. Grégoire De Nyse Et L'herméneutique Biblique Étude Des Rapports Entre Le Langage Et La Connaissance De Dieu. Paris: Etudes Augustiniennes, 1983.

Reference: Gregory of Nyssa "On the Soul and the Resurrection", Daniélou, Jean. L'être Et Le Temps Chez Grégoire De Nyse. Leiden: Brill, 1970.

Reference: Gregory of Nyssa "On the Soul and the Resurrection", Lavaud, Laurent. "L'odyssée Et L'exode : Les Mystiques De Plotin Et Grégoire De Nyse". *Le Philosophoïre* 49, no. 1 (2018): 81-91. <https://doi.org/DOI:10.3917/phoir.049.0081>.

Reference: Gregory of Nyssa "On the Soul and the Resurrection", Cavanaugh, John. St. Gregory of Nyssa on the Origin and Destiny of the Soul. Belmont, Massachusetts: Institute for Byzantine and Modern Greek Studies, 1982.

Reference: Gregory of Nyssa "On the Soul and the Resurrection", Marmodoro, Anna, and Neil McLynn. Exploring Gregory of Nyssa Philosophical, Theological, and Historical Studies. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Meredith, Anthony. The Cappadocians. Crestwood, NY: St. Vladimir's Seminary Press, 1995.

Reference: Yes, Daniélou, Jean. "La Résurrection Des Corps. Chez Grégoire De Nyse". *Vigiliae Christianae* 7, no. 3 (1953): 154-70.

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